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Professional Licensing/Register and Mutual Recognition of Academic Qualifications in the Washington Accord Jurisdictions*

D. Sánchez Ruíz
Institutional Relations Director
ICACIT
Lima, Peru
daniel.sanchez@icacit.org.pe

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INTRODUCTION

The Washington Accord was signed originally more than 25 years ago with the intention to facilitate the mutual recognition of education qualification for registering or licensing professional engineers to practice in the signatory's jurisdictions [1]. This paper seeks understand how the mutual recognition actually works inside the Washington Accord and identify which signatories are able to follow the intent of the Washington Accord.

This review is timely due to the recent admission as signatory of ICACIT (Peru) and the possible entry of three other accreditation systems from Latin America (currently as provisional members), where the register/license processes differ from those analysed in this research.

1 BACKGROUND

1.1 Washington Accord and the International Engineering Alliance

The International Engineering Alliance (IEA) is a global organization with 37 members from 28 countries around the world. The IEA comprise seven international agreements. Three of

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them for the recognition of engineering educational qualifications (Educational Accords) and the other four for recognition of professional competence (Competence Agreements).

The Washington Accord (WA) is a multi-lateral agreement between bodies responsible for accreditation or recognition of tertiary-level engineering qualifications within their jurisdictions who have chosen to work collectively to assist the mobility of professional engineers. The WA was originally signed in 1989 and is the oldest of the IEA Educational Accords.

The WA acknowledges that accreditation of engineering academic programmes is a key foundation for the practice of engineering at the professional level. Currently there are nineteen signatories and five organisations, who hold provisional signatory status

1.2 Licensing/ Register Process

The licensing is defined as the process by which a governmental agency grants official permission to persons meeting predetermined qualifications to engage in a given occupation and/or use of a particular title [2]. The register/licensing process usually requires three basic elements:

- **Academic Qualification:** educational qualifications are almost always required as a pre-requisite to demonstrate being considered for a license. In most jurisdictions, this qualification is a bachelor degree and in some jurisdictions, a master degree may be required. In many jurisdictions, licensing bodies rely on accreditation agencies to ascertain that a candidate for register/licensure possesses the required education, and most will allow graduates of accredited programs an easier path to register/licensing than others [3].
- **Experience:** usually candidates for a license are required to demonstrate that they have worked and performed successfully as engineers for a certain period of time before they apply for a license.
- **Examination:** there are a plenty of evaluation tools used by licensing bodies to assess the competence of candidates for a license. In some jurisdiction, candidates shall pass a series of standardized technical exams. In others, there is a more individual review process including an evaluation of work portfolio and interviews by peer committees. A common practice is assess in two moments: (1) after graduation for recognition of educational qualifications and (2) after complete a certain period of years working in the engineering field to demonstrate the competence for an independent practice of the engineering.

2 FRAMEWORK OF LICENSING/REGISTER PROCESSES

To understand the diversity of registration, licencing and regulatory models, a framework was establish using the criteria below and show in table 1. The information was collected through literature and websites review and consultation with Washington Accord signatories.

- a. What academic qualifications are required for Licensing/Register?
- b. How many stages and titles does the process include?
- c. How much experience is required?
- d. What kind of examination is included?
- e. There is a relation between the licensing process and accreditation?
- f. What protected title(s) and authority are provided?

Table 1. Accreditation and Registering Bodies Associated with the IEA

Jurisdiction	Academic qualification required	Stages	Experience (years)	Examination				Linked w/ accreditation	Protected Title
				Academic Qualification	Self-Assessment	Industry review	Professional Interview		
Australia	Bachelor degree	1	5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Chartered Professional Engineer (CPEng)	
Canada	Bachelor degree	2	3 - 4	Yes	-	Yes	-	Professional Engineer (P.Eng.)	
China	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Chinese Taipei	Bachelor degree	1	-	Yes	-	-	Yes	Professional Engineer	
Hong Kong	Honours degree	2	4 - 6	Yes	-	Yes	Yes	Engineer (Ir.)	
India	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Ireland	Master degree	2	4	Yes	-	Yes	Yes	Chartered Engineer (CEng MIEI)	
Japan	Bachelor degree	2	4	-	-	-	Yes	Professional Engineer (P.E.Jp)	
Korea	Bachelor degree	1	6	-	-	-	Yes	Professional Engineer	
Malaysia	Bachelor degree	2	3	-	-	Yes	Yes	Professional Engineer (Ir. / P.Eng)	
New Zealand	Bachelor degree	2	-	-	Yes	-	Yes	Chartered Professional Engineer (CPEng)	
Pakistan	Bachelor degree	2	5	-	-	-	-	Professional Engineer (PE)	
Russia	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Singapore	Bachelor degree	1	4	Yes	-	Yes	Yes	Professional Engineer (Er. / Engr.)	
South Africa	Bachelor degree	2	3	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Professional Engineer (Pr Eng)	
Sri Lanka	Bachelor degree	2	8	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Chartered Engineer [CEng (Sri Lanka)]	
Turkey	Bachelor degree	1	-	-	-	-	-	Mühendis (Engineers) / Yüksek Mühendis (Higher Engineer)	
UK	Master degree	2	-	-	-	Yes	Yes	Chartered Engineer (CEng)	
USA	Bachelor degree	2	4	Yes	-	-	Yes	Professional Engineer (PE)	

3 ANALYSIS OF THE MUTUAL RECOGNITION

The diversity of registration, licencing and regulatory models is identified as a major factor in inhibiting recognition of Accord graduates for registering/licensing. Three categories are identified to classify the regulatory models in the Washington Accord jurisdictions.

- *Signatories that are registering/licencing bodies:* A body with accreditation and registering/licencing responsibilities, in signing the Accords, agrees in terms of the Preamble and Clause 1(b) of the Accord to afford graduates of programmes accredited by other signatories the same benefits toward registration or licencing as graduates of programmes accredited in their jurisdictions. Most of these are also members of an IEA competence agreement (i.e. APEC Agreement) and operate an international register.
- *A separate registering/licencing body:* Unless a relationship exists with the jurisdiction signatory, this body may not automatically recognise programmes accredited by other Accord Signatories as meeting its educational foundation. Such a body may be a member of an IEA competence agreement and operate an international register.
- *Jurisdictions without a national licencing system:* Each state or territory has its own licencing body, establishing its own procedures and requirements for granting a professional license. In these cases, the accreditation agency usually has no authority or influence to guarantee mutual recognition.

While the Washington Accord states that each signatory will “make every reasonable effort to ensure that the bodies responsible for registering or licencing professional engineers to practice in its country or territory accept the substantial equivalence of engineering academic programmes accredited by the signatories to this agreement.” This research shows that only twelve of the nineteen signatories guarantee the recognition of accredited qualifications and two may grant it depending on the state licencing boards. Table 2 show for each Washington Accord jurisdiction, the signatory, the registering or licencing body (indicating whether it is affiliated to the IEA or not).

In third category, the cases of Canada and United States are particular because both countries has institutions which make recommendation for admission to the practice of engineering, however each state has its own agency responsible for granting licenses [4][5]. Even more interesting is the considerably variation of registration policies from state to state in USA.

In particular, in the United States, registration policies vary considerably from state to state. To illustrate, the states of Mississippi, South Carolina, South Dakota and Utah recognize the graduates of the Canadian Engineering Accrediting Board (CEAB), the states of Texas, Idaho and South Carolina recognize the programs accredited by signatories of the Washington Accord. Moreover, the state of Illinois does not necessary recognize graduates of programs accredited by ABET even when this is a common practice for the other states [6].

4 BEYOND THE RECOGNITION TO ENTRY TO THE PROFESSION

The Washington Accord signatories has no duty to provide additional benefits other than to ensure that the agencies responsible for licencing in their country or territory accept the substantial equivalence of the academic engineering programs accredited by the signatories of the Accord. Nevertheless, several signatories make efforts for recognition of academic qualifications before higher education institutions of their country to continue postgraduate studies; however, they recognize their autonomy in the admission process. In this group, Turkey and Taiwan stand out. MUDEK (Turkey) and IEET (Taiwan) through negotiations with

Table 2. Accreditation and Registering Bodies Associated with the IEA

Jurisdiction	IEA-affiliated Bodies			Non-IEA-affiliated Bodies	Mutual Recognition
	WA Signatory	Registering/ Licensing Body	Body Operating IPEA or APEC Register	Registering/ licensing Body	
Australia	Engineers Australia			–	Full recognition
Hong Kong	Hong Kong Institution of Engineers (HKIE)			–	Full recognition
Ireland	Engineers Ireland			–	Full recognition
New Zealand	Institution of Professional Engineers New Zealand (IPENZ)			–	Full recognition
Pakistan	Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC)			–	Full recognition
South Africa	Engineering Council of South Africa (ECSA)			–	Full recognition
Sri Lanka	Institution of Engineers Sri Lanka (IESL)			–	Full recognition
UK	Engineering Council (EngC) (CEng licenced to Institutions)			–	Full recognition
Malaysia	Board of Engineers Malaysia (BEM)		Institution of Engineers Malaysia	–	Full recognition
Canada	Engineers Canada	–	Engineers Canada	Provincial/Territorial Registering Bodies (15)	May require additional learning or examination
China	China Association for Science and Technology	?	–	?	Full recognition
Chinese Taipei	Institute of Engineering Education Taiwan	–	Chinese Institute of Engineers (CIE)	Ministry of Examination R.O.C	No recognition
India	National Board of Accreditation	–	Institution of Engineers India	Each municipality	No recognition
Japan	Japan Accreditation Board for Engineering Education (JABEE)	–	Institution of Professional Engineers Japan (IPEJ)	Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology	No recognition
Korea	Accreditation Board for Engineering Education of Korea (ABEEK)	–	Korean Professional Engineers Association (KPEA)	Ministry of Employment and Labour (MOEL)	No recognition
Russia	Association for Engineering Education of Russia	–	AEER	–	No recognition
Singapore	Institution of Engineers, Singapore (IES)	–	Institution of Engineers, Singapore	Professional Engineers Board (PEB)	Full recognition
Turkey	Association for Evaluation and Accreditation of Engineering Programs (MUDEK)	–	–	Turkish Union of Chambers of Engineers	Full recognition
USA	ABET Inc	–	NCEES	State Licencing Boards (54)	May require additional learning or examination

different government bodies, they have ensured mutual recognition for WA graduates to pursue postgraduate studies in the universities of their countries.

On the other hand, there are two singular cases. In Canada, CEAB establish in its accreditation criteria a process for recognition of WA studies in Canadian universities [7]. Likewise, in New Zealand WA degree holders are eligible for additional points under the Skilled Migrant immigration category [8].

5 CONCLUSIONS

Mutual recognition within the Washington Accord is not uniform. However, in some cases it goes beyond recognition for the practice of engineering for example: student mobility, postgraduate studies or even migration of professionals. Notwithstanding, this should not undervalue the worth of the Washington Accord, as a preeminent group of quality assurance organizations that has developed output standards for engineering programmes and a consensus on best practice in programme accreditation and anticipate needs in global engineering education. Therefore, it brings value to graduates and education providers by assuring that engineering accreditation system applies standards substantially equivalent to the Accord Graduate Attribute exemplar [9] as well as best practice in accrediting programmes.

Finally, indicate that the mutual recognition is not a problem unique to the Washington Accord. The EUR-ACE Accord, signed in November 2014, seeks to extend recognition of graduates for both registration / licencing and qualifications recognition purposes, also by agencies making "every reasonable effort" to ensure such recognition in their home countries [10]. Accord that may be subject of study for a future research.

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